

**The effect of 14 training sessions on the development of decision-making
skills in U-13 soccer players**

Authors:

Sixto González-Víllora^a, Guilherme Machado^{a,b,c}, Alberto Gualda^b & Israel Teoldo^b

^a EDAF Research Group, Faculty of Education, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Albacete, Spain.

^b Department of Physical Education, Centre of Research and Studies in Soccer (NUPEF), Universidade Federal de Viçosa, Viçosa, Brazil.

^c Scientific Department and Department of Athletes' Integration and Development, Paulista Football Federation (FPF), São Paulo, Brazil.

ORCID

Sixto González-Víllora – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2473-5223>

Guilherme Machado – <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5355-7679>

Israel Teoldo – <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9780-3456>

***Corresponding authors:**

Universidade Federal de Viçosa – Campus Viçosa, Department of Physical Education.
Av. PH Rolfs, S/N Campus Universitário, Viçosa-MG (Brazil). Zip Code: 36.570-900.
E-mail: machado.guilhermef@gmail.com

Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha – Facultad de Educación de Albacete.
Plaza De La Universidad, N° 3, 02006, Albacete (España).
E-mail: Sixto.gonzalez@uclm.es

The effect of 14 training sessions on the development of decision-making skills in U-13 soccer players

Abstract: Soccer is a social and sporting phenomenon. Consequently, the initiation to soccer has an educational and formative potential as a matter of teaching and training. Therefore, the objective of this study was to verify the influence of 14 sessions of a training program based on decision-making and tactical skills. Participants were 46 soccer Spanish players with a mean age of 13.18 years (SD = 0.58). Soccer players were divided into two groups: control group (23 players) and intervention group (23 players). The intervention group participated in the soccer training program based on comprehensive teaching. The evaluation instrument used to measure decision-making was TacticUP®. Results showed significant improvements in post-intervention for the quality of decision-making in the intervention group compared to the control group in tactical principles improvement on offensive and defensive skills. It is concluded that the training program improved the decision-making skills. Therefore, training programs based on comprehensive teaching applied to youth soccer schools, may be used for effective sports education.

Keywords: Tactical learning, decision-making, tactical evaluation, tactical awareness, soccer training program, sport pedagogy.

Introduction

Soccer is the most popular sport in the world, something that occurs in the same way in Spain, which is why there is an increasing demand for boys and girls to enrol in soccer schools. Moreover, parents contemplate participation in soccer for their children as recreation, as an educational tool, or simply to practice sports. The first stages of training are the fundamental basis in the formation of the athlete, where the boy or girl begins to consolidate aspects of his or her personality through socialization and its three fundamental links: family, school, and football club (Directorate of Development of the South American Football Confederation (CONMEBOL, 2020).

There are proposals for planning the soccer teaching and learning process from understanding-based approaches, but these are mainly based on the experience and knowledge of the coaches (Williams et al., 2020). In addition, the access of athletes to talent development programs depends on this subjective evaluation of the coaches (Vidigal et al., 2022), so that not all players are always benefited, since this subjective evaluation may not be correct sometimes. For this reason, sports training programs for youth players must be based on scientific evidence, beyond the coaches' subjective perception. Consequently, more studies are needed to deepen the knowledge about the development of decision-making and tactical skills in the context of soccer schools.

In soccer, decision-making skills are related to players' sport development and their ability to achieve superior performance levels (Keller et al., 2018). In this context, decision-making can be defined as an action choice, and it is an outcome that can be observed as a motor or verbal response (Bruce et al., 2012; Macmahon & Mcpherson, 2009). The coach's role as a facilitator is crucial in providing an environment that fosters players' decision-making skills (Machado, González-Víllora, Pastor-Vicedo et al., 2024;

O'Connor et al., 2016). Learning strategies that focus on developing tactical aspects in team sports are typically associated with these methodologies (Clemente et al., 2020).

The tactical dimension of soccer is directly linked to the development of decision-making skills and the formation of effective problem-solving players, as every action in the game has a tactical purpose (Teoldo et al., 2022). It is, therefore, vital to develop players' decision-making skills in line with the tactical contents recommended for each stage of their talent development pathway. Teoldo et al. (2022) argue that core tactical principles of soccer require abstract thinking and hypothesis testing to enable space occupation and movement on the field. Thus, training should initially focus on less complex principles performed within the center of play, gradually advancing to more complex principles as the child's cognitive development matures (Américo et al., 2016; Teoldo et al., 2022).

Few studies have evaluated the effectiveness of soccer interventions based on the game's core tactical principles (Lima et al., 2015; Machado, González-Villora, Roca, et al., 2024; Souza et al., 2014). These studies, conducted with U-13 (Lima et al., 2015) and U-14 (Souza et al., 2014) players, aimed to verify the effectiveness of 20 training sessions based on such tactical principles on the development of decision-making skills, assessed through tactical performance. They found that such training organization led to overall improvements in the tactical performance of players from both age groups. The study by Machado et al. (2024) was conducted with U-12 players and involved 25 training sessions based on small-sided games and tactical principles. This study confirmed improvements in cognitive and motor decision-making skills. However, while these studies indicated that training based on core tactical principles could enhance decision-making skills and tactical performance, they all involved great amount of intervention (20 to 25 training sessions) and were conducted with players from soccer clubs. It is therefore essential to

investigate other skill levels, such as players from soccer schools, who typically have fewer training sessions per week. This makes it important to explore whether interventions with fewer training sessions can effectively develop decision-making skills.

The current research seeks to contribute to the literature, implementing a 14-session training program based on decision-making considering the interaction of the players making different groups. Player interactions have been organized and planned with the aim of individualizing and responding to the player's needs. In turn, this program is evaluated by a validated instrument (TacticUP®) (Machado et al., 2020), which has not yet been carried out with an European sample. Data from an European sample may aid comparison of results across different sociocultural contexts.

Another contribution of this study is the implementation of the training program in a soccer school since most of the research about decision-making has been carried out in sports clubs or performance academies (Ashford et al., 2021). The age of the sample in this study (12 and 13 years old) has been selected because the data collection was carried out in Spain, and it is in this age category that players start to play 11-a-side soccer. Therefore, the information from this research can help youth soccer schools, soccer coaches, Physical Education teachers, and researchers, contributing to the scientific literature in the field of decision-making and training approaches based on understanding the game.

The objective of the present research is to verify the effectiveness of a training program implemented in soccer with children of the U-13 category. This training program is based on the understanding of tactics and the development of decision-making based on core tactical principles of the play outlined above, through the explanations and feedback provided by the coach, as well as individualized training where the investigation has considered both the level of development that the player has in a specific tactical

aspect, as well as the interactions between players. Therefore, an individualized sport pedagogy is carried out based on the learning that each player has. We hypothesized that intervention group with Spanish players will improve its decision-making skills, based on previous studies with similar research design and intervention program carried out with Brazilian sample and higher-level players (Machado et al., 2024).

Materials and Methods

Participants

The sample consisted of 46 male soccer school players from Spain with a mean age of 13.18 (SD = 0.58), divided into two groups: intervention group with 23 players and control group with 23 players. The group that carried out the training program was the intervention group. On the other hand, the "control" group, the team to which the training program was not applied, was the control group. The latter, except for three of its players, has players one year younger than intervention group (Control group; first-year children. Intervention group; second-year children).

The students had a heterogeneous level of expertise since this research was applied in a grassroots soccer school, and they did not carry out any prior selection process to access the different teams, because the soccer school is not dedicated to the training of elite athletes, but to education in values through sports practice and the promotion of sport.

A total of 51 participants were included at the beginning of the study, since five suffered experimental death with pre and post assessments. The experimental death were three players from the intervention group, and two players from the control group. Therefore, the final sample of the study was 46 soccer players U-13 years. Participants from the intervention group ($n = 23$) had a mean age of 13.56 (SD = 0.29) and participants

from the control group (n = 23) a mean age of 12.82 (SD = 0.33). Although the maturity was not assessed directly, the coaches informed the intervention group was slightly mature compared to the control group on their perspectives.

Both the intervention and control groups trained twice a week for 90 minutes each session, and on weekends they participated in local competition matches. These matches were played for a period of 70 minutes (35 minutes each part). As it was a soccer school, there was one coach per team. The greatest difference among groups was related to the focus of training. On the one hand, intervention group was more focused on tactical and decision-making skills development with an individual focus, on the other hand the control group had a greater focus on technical skills development (detailed information is displayed in Table 1).

The data collection was carried out with the prior authorization of the representatives of the club and the legal guardians of the children. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research with Human Beings of the leading institution (approval number: 2.312.402) and is in accordance with the standards established by the National Health Council (466/2012) and by the declaration of Helsinki (2008) for research with human beings. Moreover, an informed consent was signed by the legal guardians of the participants.

Measures and Procedures for Data Collection

Decision-making skills: TacticUP®

TacticUP® is an online platform (www.tacticup.com.br) that allows the assessment of players' decision-making skills. The validity and reliability of the TacticUP® test were shown in Machado and Teoldo (2020). In addition, this platform allows evaluating the quality and time of players decision-making skills, based on the core tactical principles of the offensive and defensive phases, in situations with and without the ball (see Figure

1) (Teoldo et al., 2022).

[FIGURE 1 NEAR HERE]

Before starting the test, the online platform displays instructions to participants regarding the test structure and procedures, and three trial scenes are exhibited to familiarize the subjects with the assessment, thus excluding the possibility of low performance due to a lack of comprehension of the task. These three trial scenes include two offensive sequences (one in which the player being observed has the ball, and another in which he is not in possession) and one defensive sequence (the player being observed is in the defensive phase of play). These three conditions enable participants to familiarize themselves with the characteristics of the video sequences they were about to watch. The test was carried out in a quiet room using iPads (iOS 12.4.5) with internet access to perform the test in the TacticUP® platform. The test took around 20 minutes per player.

The variables measured by the TacticUP® were grouped in some categories as done in previous studies (Andrade et al., 2021; Machado et al., 2020). Those categories are: 1) offensive principles inside the center of play (OICP) - penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; 2) offensive principles outside the center of play (OOCp) - width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; 3) offensive phase - all the offensive principles; 4) defensive principles inside the center of play (DICP) - delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; 5) defensive principles outside the center of play (DOCP) - defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity; 6) defensive phase – all the defensive principles; and 7) general – all the offensive and defensive principles. This categorization was performed due to the phases of the game (attack and defense) and the spatial relations between these principles and the center of play, as well as their hierarchical relationships within the teaching-learning process. The

tactical principles performed inside the center of play display less complexity regarding their execution when compared to those performed outside the center of play (Machado et al., 2020; Teoldo et al., 2022).

In addition to the variables mentioned before, we also included two other offensive categorizations for the core tactical principles, which are: 1) principles with the ball – penetration and width and length with the ball; and 2) principles without the ball – offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility, and offensive unity. These categorizations were done due to the different roles' players have to perform in the offensive phase when they possess the ball and when they must move without the ball.

The initial evaluation was applied in both groups two days before the intervention of the training program starts, and the final evaluation was carried out specifically four days after the end of the training program. Participants were evaluated in the space and took the test individually. Access to the platform was obtained through iPad iOS 12.4.5. This test, as well as the previous one, was supervised by the main researcher plus two collaborators and lasted approximately 20 minutes.

Organization of the 14 training sessions

Following the first athletes' assessment through TacticUP®, 14 training sessions were planned for the intervention and control groups. The intervention group had their sessions planned on a weekly basis according to the individual needs to improve or maintain the decision-making capacity of the participants, all of them related to the core tactical principles of soccer (see figure 1). On the contrary, the control group focused their structure on the development of technical skills based on technical exercises and circuits (see table 1).

[TABLE 1 NEAR HERE]

The sessions from the intervention group were held weekly (two sessions per week) based on the development of the players observed by the coach in training and in the matches of previous competitions. To facilitate the coach's task when giving feedback, the players were classified and ordered into two performance groups in each session depending on their results in the TacticUP® test, their level of expertise and their physical and motor development (for example, a player with high performance on principle “X”, against a player with high performance on principle “Y”). The most practical feedback was given during the training (without rest) and the most conceptual feedback at the end of the training through questions about the tactical principles developed in the activity.

During the 14 training sessions designed by the coach, he focused on the core tactical principles of soccer, to develop the decision-making skills of players. This phase of the training lasted about 35 minutes and was characterised by the use of small-sided and conditioned games. This phase was usually structured with a main activity followed by variations. The coach and researcher (same person) discussed the objectives of the trainings in planning meetings held at the beginning of each week with an international expert on the subject in charge of supervising each activity. At the end of the two training sessions of the week, a meeting was held to discuss the effectiveness of the training, how each group carried out the activities and the development of the tactical principles.

As the activities and their interactions are planned according to the players' individual needs, the amount of training time for each principle was not similar for all players, taking the 14 training sessions into account. The training time of each player, for each tactical principle, is displayed in Table 2 and the contents taught in each training session are displayed in Table 3.

[TABLE 2 NEAR HERE]

[TABLE 3 NEAR HERE]

Time control regarding the training contents taught during the 14 training sessions was carried out per player according to the groups of tactical principles, which were categorised as follows: 1) offensive principles inside the centre of play (OICP) – penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball (training time of 119.8 ± 14.5 minutes per player); 2) offensive principles outside the centre of play (OOCp) – width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity (training time of 187.5 ± 29.4 minutes per player); 3) with the ball – penetration and width and length with the ball (training time of 85.7 ± 13.9 minutes per player); 4) without the ball - offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity (training time of 221.6 ± 31.0 minutes per player); 5) defensive principles inside the centre of play (DICP) – delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance (training time of 234.2 ± 34.5 minutes per player); and 6) defensive principles outside the centre of play (DOCP) – defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity (training time of 111.6 ± 26.1 minutes per player).

Statistical analysis

Data distribution was verified through the Shapiro-Wilk test. Differences between pre-test and post-test were verified using a paired sample t-test. To make comparisons between intervention and control groups, the independent t-test was used. The significance level was considered $p < 0.05$ and the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) 22.0 software was used for the statistical procedures.

Results

The following tables show the results of the means and standard differences of the decision quality and the decision time evaluated by TacticUP® between the pretest and posttest of the intervention and control groups. The tables are represented according to the basic principles of the game, generally categorized as offensive principles inside the center of play (OICP), offensive principles outside the center of play (OOCp), principles with the ball and without the ball, principles inside defensive the center of the game (DICP), defensive principles outside the center of the game (DOCP) and an average Offensive, Defensive and General.

Pre- and post-test results of decision-making quality and time

Significant improvements were observed in the intervention group in the quality of decision-making: OOCp (59.5 ± 9.9 ; 67.3 ± 9.9 ; $p= 0.028$), Defensive (65.0 ± 6.2 ; 68.8 ± 8.2 ; $p= 0.045$) and General (68.0 ± 4.8 ; 70.7 ± 5.4 ; $p= 0.026$). No significant improvement was observed in the control group.

[TABLE 4 NEAR HERE]

Regarding the decision-making time in the intervention group, significant improvements stand out in the intervention group OOCp (9.5 ± 5.3 ; 7.0 ± 1.6 ; $p=0.025$), With the ball (10.8 ± 4.1 ; 10.2 ± 3.2 ; $p=0.003$) , Without the ball (9.6 ± 4.9 ; 7.6 ± 2.2 ; $p=0.043$), Inside the center of play (10.6 ± 4.3 ; 9.1 ± 3.6 $p=0.013$), Defensive (11.1 ± 5.1 ; 9.1 ± 3.9 ; $p= 0.006$) and General (10.5 ± 4.6 ; 8.7 ± 2.9 $p=0.015$). In the control group improvements were observed OICP (9.4 ± 2.8 ; 7.8 ± 2.0 ; $p=0.016$), OOPC (8.7 ± 2.7 ; 6.8 ± 2.4 ; $p=0.002$) With the ball (9.7 ± 2.7 ; 8.14 ± 1.66 ; $p= 0.000$), Without the ball ($8.7 \pm$

2.7; 6.9 ± 2.4 ; $p=0.001$), Offensive (9.1 ± 2.5 ; 7.3 ± 2.0 ; $p=0.001$), Defensive (9.4 ± 3.4 ; 7.5 ± 2.0 ; $p=0.006$), and General (9.2 ± 2.8 ; 7.4 ± 1.9 ; $p=0.001$).

[TABLE 5 NEAR HERE]

Quality results and time between the intervention and control group

When comparing the intervention group with the control group, there are significant differences in the quality of decision-making after applying the training program (post-test) in the following variables: DOCP⁶ (Intervention: 70.0 ± 10.8 ; Control: 62.2 ± 9.4 ; $p=0.019$), Defensive (Intervention: 68.8 ± 8.2 ; Control: 61.2 ± 8.3 ; $p=0.006$), and General (Intervention: 70.7 ± 5.4 , Control: 65.3 ± 5.7 , $p=0.004$).

[TABLE 6 NEAR HERE]

In the decision-making time, significant differences were observed in DICP⁵ both in the pretest (Intervention: 10.6 ± 4.3 ; Control: 8.1 ± 2.4 ; $p=0.030$) and in the posttest (Intervention: 9.1 ± 3.6 ; Control: 7.2 ± 2.1 ; $p=0.030$)

[TABLE 7 NEAR HERE]

Discussion

This study aimed to verify the effectiveness of a soccer training program to develop decision-making skills in U-13 youth soccer players. The hypothesis of the study was confirmed, as the results showed that the quality of decision making was more developed in the experimental group. This verifies the validity of the training program, since significant improvements are observed compared to the control group in defensive principles outside the center of the play, in defense and at a general level. Improvements

have been perceived in just 14 training sessions, and it is expected that better results would have been achieved if the training program had been prolonged over time, since according to research such as that of (Serra-Olivares & García-López, 2016), and (Roca et al., 2012) the quality and decision-making time in the game improves the greater the number of hours of training or previous experiences in soccer.

These results showed the importance of the student knowing and understanding the game, since if decision-making and tactical principles are not developed in the student, they will act uncontrollably without understanding what they are doing and why they are doing it. This precept does not involve the general concept of an athlete, so it is interesting to implement models associated with decision-making within training that involve neuroscience processes (Roca et al., 2018).

Coaches in several studies recognized the help of games in developing players' tactical intelligence and decision-making (Light & Robert, 2010; Pill, 2013; Thomas et al., 2013). Likewise, research such as that of Sánchez Sánchez et al. (2015) show that even technique can be improved by implementing tactically oriented training programs. According to Kinnerk et al. (2018), the practice must be contextualized in conditions that reproduce the game, since the transfer of skills taught in isolation to the game is relatively low. In addition, research such as that of Sánchez Sánchez et al. (2013) show that the level of fun generated through training is higher when training based on tactics is carried out compared to technique. This is one of the reasons for the individualization of the process, since these results show the importance of individualizing the stimuli provided through the training process, with respect to the individual needs of the players (Machado, González-Víllora, Roca, et al., 2024).

Hence the importance of organizing the process of player interactions with the aim of providing a more individualized and player-centered teaching-learning process,

thus giving more importance at a methodological level to the training program and bringing scientific advances for this line of investigation. It must be considered that from the age of 12-14, boys and girls can already think abstractly, so that tactical knowledge of the game can be developed, although all this also depends on important factors such as maturational development or the level of skill in the game of each player (Gutiérrez et al., 2011). This research showed that U-13 players are already capable of developing their ability to make decisions related to principles outside the center of play. Similarly, Barcellos et al. (2022) indicate that players between the ages of 11 and 12 are already capable of learning soccer content whose operationalization requires abstract thinking. The improvements in the intervention group in the offensive actions carried out outside the center of play highlight this capability.

In our study, we found similarities with previous research conducted with elite club players, particularly in terms of the capacity of young players to engage in complex decision-making processes (Barcellos et al., 2022). However, there were also notable differences. The players from soccer schools, who are generally considered to be at a lower skill level compared to elite club players, exhibited significant improvements when subjected to a well-structured training program (Gutiérrez et al., 2011). This suggests that a carefully organized and player-centered approach can have a substantial impact on their development (Machado, González-Víllora, Pastor-Vicedo, et al., 2024).

The findings indicated that structured interventions may provide an even greater benefit to players from soccer schools compared to their elite counterparts. This is likely because these players may not have had as much prior exposure to high-quality training and, therefore, stand to gain more from such an intervention (Gutiérrez et al., 2011). Moreover, improving decision-making skills and tactical understanding at this level can

enhance their overall experience and enjoyment of the sport, which is crucial for long-term engagement and development (Teoldo et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the structured training programs tailored to the developmental stages and individual needs of these players can foster a more inclusive and effective learning environment. This approach not only contributes to better skill acquisition but also promotes a positive sporting experience, encouraging continued participation and improvement (Clemente et al., 2020). These results underline the potential for significant advancements in training methodologies, particularly for youth players in soccer schools, and emphasize the need for further research in this area to optimize training processes and outcomes (Machado, González-Víllora, Roca, et al., 2024).

The results revealed that decision-making time improved significantly in some areas but not others. Specifically, improvements were noted in offensive actions outside the center of play and in defensive actions inside the center of play in the intervention group. These results align with previous research, which suggests that the quality of decision-making and response time in sports can be influenced by the amount and quality of training (Machado et al., 2020; Teoldo et al., 2022). The observed improvements are likely due to the structured and consistent nature of the training sessions, which emphasized core tactical principles and small-sided games.

We found no improvement in some aspects, like the quality of decision-making in principles with the ball. It can be explained by different reasons. Previous literature shows that the quality of decision-making usually develops in slower pace compared to decision-making time (Machado et al., 2024), and principles without the ball develop quicker compared to principles with the ball (Barcellos et al., 2022). Additionally, the results from our study might suggest that improvements in principles with the ball might

take longer training volumes than the players had on the other categories of tactical principles, which varied between ~72 to ~107 minutes in the present study (see Table 2).

Furthermore, our results indicated that decision-making time with the ball also improved, reflecting a more efficient and faster processing of game situations. This improvement is crucial as it allows players to execute decisions quicker, which is essential in high-paced game scenarios (Machado et al., 2023). On the contrary, the decision-making time inside the center of play did not improve as much, possibly due to the higher cognitive load and pressure in these situations, which might require more specific drills and extended training periods to enhance (Teoldo et al., 2023).

The methodology used in this study, focusing on individualized and player-centered training, can be effectively applied in various contexts to improve decision-making skills in soccer players from different backgrounds, such as soccer schools and clubs. Our findings suggest that structured interventions based on core tactical principles are particularly beneficial for players in soccer schools, who may have less exposure to high-quality training compared to their counterparts in elite clubs (Gutiérrez et al., 2011).

The focus on both proximal (near the ball) and distal (far from the ball) decision-making skills is crucial for the holistic development of players, ensuring they can perform effectively in different game situations (Roca & Ford, 2020). By implementing similar training programs in soccer schools, coaches can enhance the players' tactical understanding and decision-making abilities, thereby improving their overall experience and engagement in the sport. This approach not only contributes to better skill acquisition but also promotes a positive sporting experience, encouraging continued participation and improvement (Clemente et al., 2020).

This is the first empirical study conducted with players from a soccer school, rather than from a competitive club, to assess the impact of an intervention based on

tactical principles on decision-making skills. It demonstrates the feasibility of evaluating decision-making abilities and the subsequent learning of these skills at this age. Consequently, it contributes to the scientific literature supporting this claim. Additionally, this study is novel in being the first to use the TacticUP® evaluation tool with an European sample.

In summary, the effectiveness of the training program has been demonstrated, where the contents that have stood out the most for their learning have been the principles furthest from the center of the game, since this learning stage must be used by the coach to develop the actions carried out outside the center of play (González-Víllora et al., 2012). Therefore, the results of this study support this recommendation through the scientific literature, thus reinforcing the importance of teaching content related to actions further away from the ball (outside the center of play) in training, in early stages, since that players already have the necessary skills to assimilate these principles (González-Víllora et al., 2012).

For future research, it is important to evaluate the decision-making of players to tailor the stimuli to both the individual needs of players and the collective needs of the team. The evaluation instruments used must be appropriate for the age and developmental stage of the players. For instance, TacticUP® can be used in players starting from 10/11 years old to assess core tactical principles, while GPET can be more suitable for younger players (around 6-12 years old) to assess operational tactical principles. In addition to using these validated and reliable tactical and decision-making evaluation instruments, it is recommended to conduct new studies across different age groups and contexts, such as schools, soccer schools, and sports clubs.

Conducting such analyses in soccer schools is particularly relevant, as these institutions are primarily responsible for teaching soccer to boys and girls, most of whom

are found in soccer schools rather than high-performance clubs. It is also recommended in future research to deepen the development and acquisition of decision-making skills, with different characteristics of the sample, such as different competitive levels, age, gender, historical profile, and players from different countries. One innovative aspect of this study is the use of the TacticUP® tactical analysis evaluation instrument with an European sample of Spanish players for the first time, as previous data were only available for South American samples. This is significant as it allows for the comparison of results across different sociocultural contexts.

The limitations of the study are shown in some experimental deaths of the initial sample, since in a soccer school child sometimes leave the team or stop going to training for a season, generally based on their academic results and/or personal issues. Finally, the data was taken from a small-medium soccer school in Spain, considering that soccer schools usually have these dimensions, it was decided to take data in the same category one year apart because the coach and the social context and culture of the children was the same. Although the TacticUP® has not limitations to be used as an assessment tool in other countries, it was developed based on core tactical principles, which are frequently trained in Portugal and Brazil (González-Víllora & Teoldo, 2015; Teoldo et al., 2022). However, due to cultural differences, coaches in central and northern European countries may not apply these concepts as commonly. Although these limitations, the results of this study provide us with highly relevant pedagogical guidance on the soccer training process.

Practical Applications

The findings of this study have significant practical implications for coaches, technical directors, and soccer development programs. The results highlight the effectiveness of implementing training programs focused on decision-making and tactical principles, even

in soccer school settings with players who typically have less exposure to structured training methodologies. Coaches can use these insights to design training interventions that not only improve tactical understanding but also enhance the overall decision-making skills, particularly in more complex scenarios as those far from the ball. The use of the methodology to assess and develop the training program of this study can also be used in school's context, considering that little technology is needed to implement this. Only access to a computer or a tablet and internet is necessary to carry out the assessment followed by the organization of training structure focused on the individual need of players/students made throughout tactical concepts and active methodologies like game-centred approaches (González-Villora et al., 2020) or sport education (Sientop et al., 2019).

While this study focused on soccer school players in Spain, the structured and individualized approach presented here can be adapted to different contexts, such as elite soccer clubs, players from various age groups, and even other countries, particularly those with cultural similarities to Spain. For instance, Roca and Ford (2020) demonstrated that Portuguese and Spanish training structures share significant similarities. Similarly, Machado et al. (2024) found strong parallels between training settings in Brazil and Spain and Ford et al (2020) similar sport pathways in Portugal, Mexico, and Ghana. These findings suggest that this tactical training approach, rooted in core principles, may be reasonably applicable across similar cultural contexts.

The study also reinforces the utility of the TacticUP® assessment tool in providing reliable and actionable data to evaluate and improve players' decision-making skills. Coaches and sports educators are encouraged to integrate objective assessment tools, like TacticUP® into their training processes, as it offers a practical way to measure

both the quality and speed of decision-making. This facilitates more targeted interventions tailored to the individual needs of players.

Conclusion

In summary, it is drawn that the implementation of the training program designed in this work improves decision-making skills. Therefore, players should be given learning in a contextualized and individualized environment. For this, it is necessary to carry out objective and scientifically validated evaluations of the decision making of the players so that training can be applied that is compatible with their individual improvement needs.

This training program based on decision-making and understanding of tactics can also be carried out in soccer schools, since the individualization of the process according to the tactical needs of the child helps to develop the core tactical principles of play, this could provide soccer schools the possibility of working with heterogeneous groups depending on the level of expertise without problems in terms of the fluidity of the game.

It is also highlighted that the core tactical principles that are further away from the ball (outside the center of play) can be developed with U-13 players, as well as consolidate the principles closest to the ball, which are already more familiar to them, because they are the first to be learned on earlier stages. The fact of demonstrating that it is possible to teach the tactical principles outside the center of play in U-13 players is something fundamental to consider in soccer teaching programs, and in this way to be able to sequence the tactical learning of players in training in an appropriate way in terms of difficulty.

References

- Américo, H. B., Cardoso, F. da S. L., Machado, G. F., Andrade, M. O. C., Resende, E. R., & Teoldo, I. C. (2016). Analysis of the tactical behavior of youth academy soccer players. *Journal of Physical Education*, 27(1), e-2710. <https://doi.org/10.4025/jphyseduc.v27i1.2710>
- Andrade, L., Machado, G., Gonçalves, E., & Teoldo, I. (2021). Decision making in soccer: effect of positional role of U-13 soccer players. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 21(3), 1413–1420. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2021.03180>
- Ashford, M., Abraham, A., & Poolton, J. (2021). A Communal Language for Decision Making in Team Invasion Sports. *International Sport Coaching Journal*, 8(1), 122–129. <https://doi.org/10.1123/iscj.2019-0062>
- Barcellos, A., Teoldo, I., & Machado, G. (2022). The influence of 25 training sessions on the decision-making skill of U-12 soccer players. *Psicologia: Teoria e Pesquisa*, 38, e38211. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0102.3772e38211.en>
- Bruce, L., Farrow, D., Raynor, A., & Mann, D. (2012). But I can't pass that far! The influence of motor skill on decision making. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 13(2), 152–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2011.10.005>
- Clemente, F. M., Afonso, J., Castillo, D., Arcos, A. L., Silva, A. F., & Sarmiento, H. (2020). The effects of small-sided soccer games on tactical behavior and collective dynamics: A systematic review. *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 134, 109710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.109710>
- Ford, P. R., Carling, C., Garces, M., Marques, M., Miguel, C., Farrant, A., Stenling, A., Moreno, J., Gall, F. Le, Holmström, S., Salmela, J., & Williams, A. M. (2012). The developmental activities of elite soccer players aged under-16 years from Brazil, England, France, Ghana, Mexico, Portugal and Sweden. *Journal of Sports Sciences*,

- 30(15), 1653–1663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2012.701762>
- CONMEBOL. (2020). *Manual Orientador*. Nobel Indústria Gráfica.
- González-Víllora, S., Fernandez-Rio, F. J. Guijarro, E., & Sierra-Díaz, M. J. (2020). *The Game-Centred Approach to Sport Literacy*. Routledge.
- González-Víllora, S., García-López, L. M., Gutiérrez, D., & Pastor, J. C. (2012). Estudio del rendimiento de juego (2 vs. 2) en jugadores de fútbol con 8 años. *Revista de Investigación en Educación*, 10(1), 115–126.
- González-Víllora, S. & Teoldo, I. (2015). ¿Cómo evaluar la táctica en fútbol? Sistema de evaluación de la táctica en fútbol (Fut-Sat). *Educación Física y Deporte*, 34 (2), 467-505. <http://doi.org/10.17533/udea.efyd.v34n2a08>
- Gutiérrez, D., González-Víllora, S., García-López, L., & Mitchell, S. (2011). Differences in decision-making development between expert and novice invasion game players. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 112(3), 871–888. <https://doi.org/10.2466/05.10.11.25.PMS.112.3.871-888>
- Keller, B. S., Raynor, A. J., Iredale, F., & Bruce, L. (2018). Tactical skill in Australian youth soccer: Does it discriminate age-match skill levels? *International Journal of Sports Science and Coaching*, 13(6), 1057–1063. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747954118760778>
- Kinnerk, P., Harvey, S., MacDonncha, C., & Lyons, M. (2018). A review of the game-based approaches to coaching literature in competitive team sport settings. *Quest*, 70(4), 401–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2018.1439390>
- Light, R. L., & Robert, J. E. (2010). The impact of Game Sense pedagogy on Australian rugby coaches' practice: A question of pedagogy. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 15(2), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408980902729388>
- Lima, R. C., Cardoso, F. S. L., Vecchi, P., Teoldo, I. C., & Paoli, P. B. (2015). A

organização do treino baseado nos princípios fundamentais do jogo de futebol e sua relação com o desempenho tático de jogadores da categoria sub 13. *Revista Brasileira de Futebol*, 8(1), 30–42.

Machado, G., González-Víllora, S., & Teoldo, I. (2023). The relationship between deliberate practice, play, and futsal in childhood and adolescence and the development of different decision-making skills in professional female soccer players. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102470>

Machado, G., González-Víllora, S., Pastor-Vicedo, J. C., & Teoldo, I. (2024). Mapping talent pathways: A comparative study of developmental activities and practice structure in Brazilian and Spanish U-18 elite youth male soccer players. *International Journal of Sports Science and Coaching*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17479541241241487>

Machado, G., González-Víllora, S., Roca, A., & Teoldo, I. (2024). Developing cognitive and motor decision-making skills through tactical principles and small-sided games in youth soccer. *International Journal of Performance Analysis in Sport*, 24(05), 44–463. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24748668.2024.2321039>

Machado, G., & Teoldo, I. (2020). TacticUP Video Test for Soccer: Development and validation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01690>

Macmahon, C., & Mcpherson, S. U. E. L. (2009). Knowledge base as a mechanism for perceptual-cognitive tasks: Skill is in the details! *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 40(4), 565–579.

O'Connor, D., Larkin, P., & Mark Williams, A. (2016). Talent identification and selection in elite youth football: An Australian context. *European Journal of Sport Science*,

- 16(7), 837–844. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2016.1151945>
- Pill, S. (2013). Using Appreciative Inquiry to explore Australian football coaches' experience with game sense coaching. *Sport, Education and Society*, 20(6), 799–818. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2013.831343>
- Roca, A., & Ford, P. R. (2020). Decision-making practice during coaching sessions in elite youth football across European countries. *Science and Medicine in Football*, 4(4), 263–268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2020.1755051>
- Roca, A., Ford, P. R., & Memmert, D. (2018). Creative decision making and visual search behavior in skilled soccer players. *PLoS ONE*, 13(7), e0199281. <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0199381>
- Roca, A., Williams, A. M., & Ford, P. R. (2012). Developmental activities and the acquisition of superior anticipation and decision making in soccer players. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 30(15), 1643–1652. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2012.701761>
- Sánchez Sánchez, J., Yagüe Cabezón, J. M., & Molinero González, O. (2013). Enjoy level research generated by technical and tactical training programs in young soccer players. *Cuadernos de Psicología Del Deporte*, 13(1), 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.4321/S1578-84232013000100010>
- Sánchez Sánchez, J., Molinero González, O., & Yagüe Cabezón, J. M. (2015). Effects of two training-learning methodologies on the individual technique of players from 6 to 10 years old. *Retos*, 2041(22), 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v0i22.34580>
- Serra-Olivares, J., & García-López, L. M. (2016). Design and validation of the soccer tactical knowledge test (STKT). *Revista Internacional de Medicina y Ciencias de La Actividad Física y Del Deporte*, 16(63), 521–536. <https://doi.org/10.15366/rimcafd2016.63.008>

- Siedentop, D., Hastie, P., & Van der Mars, H. (2019). *Complete guide to sport education*. Human Kinetics.
- Souza, C., Muller, E., Teoldo, I., & Graça, A. (2014). Quais comportamentos táticos de jogadores de futebol da categoria sub-14 podem melhorar após 20 sessões de treino? *Revista Brasileira de Ciências Do Esporte*, 36(1), 71–86. [internal-pdf://121.226.169.207/173-2014-Quais-comportamentos-taticos-de-joga.pdf](https://doi.org/10.12733/173-2014-Quais-comportamentos-taticos-de-joga.pdf)
- Teoldo, I., Guilherme, J., & Garganta, J. (2022). *Football Intelligence: Training and Tactics for Soccer Success*. Routledge.
- Teoldo, Israel, Mezzadri, I., Cardoso, F., & Machado, G. (2023). *Speed of decision-making as a key element for professional and academy soccer players' performances*. *Retos*, 50(4), 1195–1203. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v50.100355](https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v50.100355)
- Thomas, G., Morgan, K., & Mesquita, I. (2013). Examining the implementation of a Teaching Games for Understanding approach in junior rugby using a reflective practice design. *Sports Coaching Review*, 2(1), 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21640629.2013.855000>
- Vidigal, E. C., Silva, F. F., Rodrigues, T. L. A., Ribeiro Júnior, D. B., Matta, M. de O., de Barros, A. N., Gonçalves, M. C., Coelho, E. F., & Werneck, F. Z. (2022). “Coach’s eye”: psychological and tactical skills discriminate sporting potential of young soccer players. *Revista Brasileira de Cineantropometria e Desempenho Humano*, 24, e91439. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-0037.2022v24e91439>
- Williams, A. M., Ford, P. R., & Drust, B. (2020). Talent identification and development in soccer since the millennium. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 38(11–12), 1199–1210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2020.1766647>

Figure 1

Description of the core tactical principles of soccer: a) offensive; and b) defensive

a) Offensive Principles

b) Defensive Principles

Note: Adapted from Football Intelligence (p. 30), by Teoldo, Guilherme & Garganta, 2022, Routledge.

Table 1. Training structure of the control and intervention group

Structure	Control		Intervention	
	T (min)	Training	T (min)	Training
Warm up	15	Joint mobility, coordination	10	Joint mobility, coordination
Ball warm up	15	Technique exercises	10	Technique exercises
Main part	20	Technical circuit	35	Training based on tactical principles
	40	Match	35	Match

Table 2. Training time per principle and per player in the intervention group

Principles	Players (Without goalkeeper) – time per each principle (minutes)																		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
Offensive																			
Penetration	54	72	71	89	89	89	69	71	54	54	72	71	74	36	72	69	72	54	54
Offensive coverage	36	36	18	36	36	36	36	18	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36
Width and length with the ball	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
Width and length without the ball	54	72	18	72	36	54	36	72	54	36	54	54	36	36	54	56	72	54	72
Mobility	54	54	90	36	36	72	90	56	92	36	72	72	87	36	90	90	72	72	36
Offensive unity	54	72	54	89	54	89	89	54	54	89	72	72	89	54	72	72	72	72	54
OICP ¹	108	126	107	143	143	143	123	107	108	108	126	125	128	90	126	123	126	108	108
OOC ²	162	198	162	197	126	215	215	182	200	161	198	198	212	126	216	218	216	198	162
With the ball ³	72	90	89	107	107	107	87	89	72	72	90	89	92	54	90	87	90	72	72
Without the ball ⁴	198	234	180	233	162	251	251	200	236	197	234	234	248	162	252	254	252	234	198
Defensive																			
Delay	125	90	90	90	90	90	110	87	105	125	90	72	87	124	108	90	108	125	125
Defensive Coverage	90	54	54	72	108	72	74	54	90	125	72	72	54	107	90	72	90	90	72
Recovery Balance	89	54	72	54	54	54	54	54	54	36	36	54	36	36	54	54	54	54	54
Defensive Balance	18	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	18	18	0	35	18	18	18	18	35
Concentration	54	54	36	54	54	54	54	54	54	36	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54
Defensive Unity	36	54	36	36	36	36	36	36	54	36	54	54	36	71	54	54	54	54	71
DICP ⁵	304	198	216	216	252	216	238	195	249	286	198	198	177	267	252	216	252	269	251
DOCP ⁶	108	126	72	90	90	90	90	90	126	72	126	126	90	160	126	126	126	126	160

¹ principles of penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; ² principles of width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ³ principles of penetration and width and length with the ball; ⁴ principles of offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ⁵ principles of delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; and ⁶ principles of defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity.

Table 3. Time and contents per training session

Session	Tactical principle	Time (min)
1	Penetration, Offensive coverage, Delay, Defensive coverage	35
2	Mobility, Penetration, Balance Recovery, Delay	35
3	Offensive Unity, Mobility, Defensive Unit, Defensive Balance	35
4	Defensive Cover, Offensive Cover, Delay, Balance Recovery	35
5	Penetration, Delay	35
6	Defensive Cover, Offensive Cover, Delay, Penetration	35
7	Defensive Unity, Offensive Unity	35
8	Width and length with the ball, Mobility, Defensive coverage	35
9	Width and length with the ball, Width and length without the ball, Delay	35
10	Width and length without the ball, Concentration	35
11	Mobility, Concentration, Recovery Balance	35
12	Defensive Unity, Offensive Unity	35
13	Defensive Coverage, Offensive Coverage	35
14	Mobility, Recovery Balance, Concentration	35

Table 4. Mean and standard deviation of the quality of decision-making between the pretest and posttest of the intervention and control groups.

Indexes	Intervention Group (n = 20)			Control Group (n = 20)		
	Pretest	Posttest	p	Pretest	Posttest	p
QUALITY OF DECISION MAKING (a.u.)						
<u>Offensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ¹	82.3 ± 9.7	78.0 ± 11.2	0.062	74.4 ± 9.5	75.6 ± 9.0	0.583
Outside the center of play ²	59.5 ± 9.9	67.3 ± 9.9	0.028*	63.3 ± 10.2	63.1 ± 8.0	0.957
With the ball ³	83.6 ± 10.2	78.9 ± 11.5	0.104	81.2 ± 11.5	77.9 ± 10.8	0.329
Without the ball ⁴	64.6 ± 7.3	69.5 ± 9.7	0.100	62.7 ± 8.2	65.1 ± 6.2	0.301
Offensive	70.9 ± 5.7	72.7 ± 8.7	0.413	68.8 ± 5.8	69.4 ± 5.2	0.724
<u>Defensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ⁵	60.1 ± 12.7	64.5 ± 13.8	0.253	62.3 ± 14.3	63.0 ± 10.8	0.861
Outside the center of play ⁶	66.0 ± 8.3	70.0 ± 10.8	0.137	66.8 ± 11.3	62.2 ± 9.4	0.150
Defensive	65.0 ± 6.2	68.8 ± 8.2	0.045*	65.1 ± 9.6	61.2 ± 8.3	0.169
<u>General</u>						
General	68.0 ± 4.8	70.7 ± 5.4	0.026*	67.0 ± 6,3	65.3 ± 5.7	0.351

*p < 0.05; a.u. - arbitrary units; ¹ principles of penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; ² principles of width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ³ principles of penetration and width and length with the ball; ⁴ principles of offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ⁵ principles of delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; and ⁶ principles of defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity.

Table 5. Mean and standard deviation of decision-making time between the pretest and posttest of the intervention and control groups.

Indexes	Intervention Group (n = 20)			Control Group (n = 20)		
	Pretest	Posttest	p	Pretest	Posttest	p
DECISION MAKING TIME (s)						
<u>Offensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ¹	10.4 ± 3.9	9.9 ± 3.2	0.469	9.4 ± 2.8	7.8 ± 2.0	0.016*
Outside the center of play ²	9.5 ± 5.3	7.0 ± 1.6	0.025*	8.7 ± 2.7	6.8 ± 2.4	0.002*
With the ball ³	10.8 ± 4.1	10.2 ± 3.2	0.003*	9.7 ± 2.7	8.14 ± 1.66	0.000*
Without the ball ⁴	9.6 ± 4.9	7.6 ± 2.2	0.043*	8.7 ± 2.7	6.9 ± 2.4	0.001*
Offensive	10.0 ± 4.4	8.4 ± 2.2	0.061	9.1 ± 2.5	7.3 ± 2.0	0.001*
<u>Defensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ⁵	10.6 ± 4.3	9.1 ± 3.6	0.013*	8.1 ± 2.4	7.2 ± 2.1	0,105
Outside the center of play ⁶	10.8 ± 4.9	9.4 ± 4.2	0.073	8.5 ± 2.3	7.7 ± 2.3	0.101
Defensive	11.1 ± 5.1	9.1 ± 3.9	0.006*	9.4 ± 3.4	7.5 ± 2.0	0.006*
<u>General</u>						
General	10.5 ± 4.6	8.7 ± 2.9	0.015*	9.2 ± 2.8	7.4 ± 1.9	0.001*

*p < 0.05; ¹ principles of penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; ² principles of width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ³ principles of penetration and width and length with the ball; ⁴ principles of offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ⁵ principles of delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; and ⁶ principles of defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity.

Table 6. Mean and standard deviation of the quality of decision-making between the intervention and control groups in the pretest and posttest.

Indexes	Pretest			Posttest		
	Intervention	Control	p	Intervention	Control	p
QUALITY OF DECISION MAKING (a. u.)						
<u>Offensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ¹	82.3 ± 9.7	74.4 ± 9,5	0.013*	78.0 ± 11.2	75.6 ± 9.0	0.446
Outside the center of play ²	59.5 ± 9.9	63.3 ± 10.2	0.244	67.3 ± 9.9	63.1 ± 8.0	0.151
With the ball ³	83.6 ± 10.2	81.2 ± 11.5	0.492	78.9 ± 11.5	77.9 ± 10.8	0.764
Without the ball ⁴	64.6 ± 7.3	62.7 ± 8.2	0.446	69.5 ± 9.7	65.1 ± 6.2	0.095
Offensive	70.9 ± 5.7	68.8 ± 5.8	0.268	72.7 ± 8.7	69.4 ± 5.2	0.155
<u>Defensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ⁵	60.1 ± 12.7	62.3 ± 14,3	0.611	64.5 ± 13.8	63.0 ± 10.8	0.712
Outside the center of play ⁶	66.0 ± 8.3	66.8 ± 11.3	0.822	70.0 ± 10.8	62.2 ± 9.4	0.019*
Defensive	65.0 ± 6.2	65.1 ± 9.6	0.973	68.8 ± 8.2	61.2 ± 8.3	0.006*
<u>General</u>						
General	68.0 ± 4.8	67.0 ± 6.3	0.583	70.7 ± 5.4	65.3 ± 5.7	0.004*

*p < 0.05; a.u. - arbitrary units; ¹ principles of penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; ² principles of width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ³ principles of penetration and width and length with the ball; ⁴ principles of offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ⁵ principles of delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; and ⁶ principles of defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity.

Table 7. Mean and standard deviation of decision-making time between the intervention and control groups in the pretest and posttest.

Indexes	Pretest			Posttest		
	Intervention	Control	p	Intervention	Control	p
DECISION MAKING TIME (s)						
<u>Offensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ¹	10.4 ± 3.9	9.4 ± 2,8	0.334	9.9 ± 3.2	7.8 ± 2.0	0.334
Outside the center of play ²	9.5 ± 5.3	8.7 ± 2,7	0.573	7.0 ± 1.6	6.8 ± 2.4	0.573
With the ball ³	10.8 ± 4.1	9.7 ± 2,7	0.336	10.2 ± 3.2	8.14 ± 1.66	0.336
Without the ball ⁴	9.6 ± 4.9	8.7 ± 2,7	0.514	7.6 ± 2.2	6.9 ± 2.4	0.514
Offensive	10.0 ± 4.4	9.1 ± 2,5	0.430	8.4 ± 2.2	7.3 ± 2.0	0.107
<u>Defensive</u>						
Inside the center of play ⁵	10.6 ± 4.3	8.1 ± 2.4	0.030*	9.1 ± 3.6	7.2 ± 2.1	0.030*
Outside the center of play ⁶	10.8 ± 4.9	8.5 ± 2.3	0.073	9.4 ± 4.2	7.7 ± 2.3	0.073
Defensive	11.1 ± 5.1	9.4 ± 3.4	0.216	9.1 ± 3.9	7.5 ± 2.0	0.106
<u>General</u>						
General	10.5 ± 4.6	9.2 ± 2.8	0.280	8.7 ± 2.9	7.4 ± 1.9	0.089

*p < 0.05; ¹ principles of penetration, offensive coverage and width and length with the ball; ² principles of width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ³ principles of penetration and width and length with the ball; ⁴ principles of offensive coverage, width and length without the ball, mobility and offensive unity; ⁵ principles of delay, defensive coverage and recovery balance; and ⁶ principles of defensive balance, concentration and defensive unity.